

IBISBA 1.0

Industrial Biotechnology Innovation and Synthetic Biology Accelerator

Deliverable D7.3

IBISBAHub Workflow Repository and Portal

Planned delivery date (as in DoA): M30

Actual submission date: 17/11/2020, month M36

Workpackage: WP7

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Version: 1.0

Dissemination Level	
PU Public	X
CI Classified, as referred to Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

This deliverable is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 730976.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction	3
2	Current status	4
3	Evolution of IBISBA 1.0 ecosystem	5
3.1	IBISBAHub	5
3.2	WorkflowHub	6
3.3	RO-Crate	7
3.4	Schema.org annotation	7
3.5	Bio.tools and the EDAM ontology	8
4	Handbook	9
5	User engagement	10
6	Collaboration with wider community	10
6.1	SEEK Committees	10
6.2	WorkflowHub Club	11
6.3	Bioschemas Community	11
6.4	Biohackathons	11
6.5	Research Object Communities	12
7	Future work	12
7.1	Workflow execution	12
7.2	Investigation planning and enactment	12
7.3	Protocols	12
7.4	BPM execution	13
8	Partners involved in the work	13

1 Introduction

The IBISBAHub¹ is a shared space for recording, accessing and sharing data and assets of the IBISBA project. IBISBAHub is a customised and extended installation of the FAIRDOM SEEK asset management platform².

The IBISBAHub provides an online portal with

- Self-managed project space for organising, sharing and disseminating assets arising from multi-partner collaborations, such as the TNA's as well as project events
- Complement local data management or provide data management resources if local resources are absent
- Store and register standardised protocols, computational workflows and data format templates
- Rich standards-based metadata describes and interrelates different asset types: samples, organisms, models, protocols, data and documents
- Integration with third party tools such as modelling tools (e.g. JWS Online³), metadata capture tools (e.g. Rightfield⁴) and development repositories (e.g. GitHub⁵)
- A reporting resource for IBISBA to the EU and to the ESFRI

The IBISBAHub is described in the IBISBA Handbook⁶ (see below)

IBISBAHub supports an OpenAPI⁷ and JSONAPI⁸ conformant interface that supports secured programmatic access for other tools.

¹ <https://hub.ibisba.eu>

² <https://seek4science.org/>

³ <https://jji.mib.ac.uk/>

⁴ <https://rightfield.org.uk/>

⁵ <https://github.com/nf-core>

⁶ <https://ibisba.github.io/handbook/index.html>

⁷ <https://swagger.io/specification/>

⁸ <https://jsonapi.org/>

2 Current status

- The 16 institutions that are part of IBISBA are registered in IBISBAHub.
- Accounts have been created for the IBISBA participants, and 63 people are registered.
- The IBISBAHub is structured into levels with the Programme being the highest level of organisation followed by the Projects and then the Investigation→ Study→ Assay (ISA) framework⁹
- Two main programmes have been created:
 - The shared IBISBA programme that contains two main sections
 - A library of templates for data
 - A library of reusable assets including
 - over 90 laboratory protocols
 - 20+ computational workflow nodes (tools) and
 - 8 computational workflows
 - One for TNA-specific content that contains
 - Projects for all of the round 1, 2 and 3 TNAs

There is a standard template for the IBISBA protocols, along with a guideline document. WP6 are discussing how to curate and ensure standardization of the protocols. The IBISBA workflows are described in IBISBA MS35.

⁹ <https://ibisba.github.io/handbook/>

Figure 1. Project structure for a TNA project

3 Evolution of IBISBA 1.0 ecosystem

While the project has been running, the "ecosystem" of applications and standards in the domain has, inevitably, evolved. (Some of these changes have been driven by collaboration in developing solutions for the Covid 19 virus.) IBISBA WP7 has adopted the agile approach of leveraging these developments.

3.1 IBISBAHub

From the outset, IBISBAHub has interfaced with external resources.

- people can reference their ORCID
- organisms can be identified by their NCBI taxon id
- publications are identified by a DOI or a PubMed ID
- models may be run on a JWSONline server
- assets are given a referenced license
- DOIs can be generated using DataCite

Apart from the creation of IBISBAHub itself, there are four significant developments that WP7 consider to affect IBISBA:

- WorkflowHub

- Research Objects and RO-Crate
- schema.org and Bioschemas.org annotation
- bio.tools

These are discussed in detail below.

3.2 WorkflowHub

The WorkflowHub¹⁰ is a FAIR workflow registry sponsored by the European RI Cluster EOSC-Life and the ELIXIR Research Infrastructure, and forms part of the EOSC-Life WP2 Tools Collaboratory. It is an evolution from the myExperiment application.

WorkflowHub is workflow system agnostic, and supports a registry of computational workflows in native, e.g. Galaxy¹¹ or Nextflow¹², and standardised form - Common Workflow Language¹³ (CWL). In addition to a browser-based UI, the registry supports an OpenAPI and JSONAPI conformant interface that supports programmatic access for tool developers.

The workflows are also exposed by WorkflowHub with schema.org annotations (see below), that include references to the EDAM ontology¹⁴.

WorkflowHub also supports the GA4GH¹⁵ Tool Registry Service (TRS)¹⁶

The WorkflowHub is supported by a diverse community¹⁷

Impact on IBISBA

Developers of workflows would be inconvenienced if there were several sites where they should register workflows - IBISBAHub and WorkflowHub. There would likely be confusion for both workflow developers and users over versioning, ownership, annotation etc.

WorkflowHub has a community dedicated to supporting the registration of workflows. It would not be sensible to split or duplicate development activity.

For the above reasons it was decided that **the WorkflowHub will be the canonical registry of workflows.** The IBISBA relevant workflows will be grouped in the IBISBA Team on WorkflowHub.

¹⁰ <https://workflowhub.eu/>

¹¹ <https://galaxyproject.org/>

¹² <https://www.nextflow.io/>

¹³ <https://www.commonwl.org/>

¹⁴ <http://edamontology.org>

¹⁵ <https://www.ga4gh.org/>

¹⁶ <https://ga4gh.github.io/tool-registry-service-schemas/>

¹⁷ <https://about.workflowhub.eu/acknowledgements/>

IBISBAHub will present its users with "proxies" to the workflows; the workflows will always remain on WorkflowHub.

3.3 RO-Crate

Research Objects¹⁸ are an initiative to group together the information about a piece of research. Research Object Crate¹⁹ (RO-Crate) is a community effort to establish a lightweight approach to packaging Research Objects. It is based on schema.org annotations (see below) in JSON for Linking Data (JSON-LD).

RO-Crate aims to make best-practice in formal metadata description accessible and practical for use in a wider variety of situations, from an individual researcher working with a folder of data, to large data-intensive computational research environments.

Different types of research data will have different classes of associated information. The content of an RO-Crate for computational (as distinct from laboratory) workflows²⁰ has been specified. In addition to the workflow itself, the RO-Crate can contain, for example, a diagram showing a user-relevant presentation of the workflow.

The WorkflowHub supports the generation of RO-Crates for registered workflows, as well as the export of such RO-Crates.

Impact on IBISBA

RO-Crates that conform to the workflow profile provide a strong alternative to the interchange of the "bare" workflows themselves. IBISBA would benefit from RO-Crate centric developments; already a workflow testing environment is being developed using RO-Crate.

In addition, the RO-Crate workflow profile will be extended to support:

1. the submission of a workflow with input data to a workflow executor
2. the acceptance of the results of workflow execution.

For these reasons, IBISBA WP7 intends to support the reading of workflows from WorkflowHub as RO-Crates. We will display the status of any workflow testing. We will also investigate the submission and acceptance of workflow executions using RO-Crate.

3.4 Schema.org annotation

"Schema.org is a collaborative, community activity with a mission to create, maintain, and promote schemas for structured data on the Internet, on web pages, in email messages, and beyond." Initially founded by Google, Microsoft, Yahoo and Yandex, schema.org is developed by an Open Source community.

¹⁸ <https://www.researchobject.org/>

¹⁹ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

²⁰ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/1.1-DRAFT/workflows.html>

The annotations allow data on the web to be searched in a semantically meaningful manner, rather than just as "dumb text". For example, Dataset Search²¹ allows the searching for sets of data.

schema.org allows a large number of properties that may be specified for an object. For example, Organization²² has over 100 properties. All of these properties are optional; schema.org annotation only mandates the specification of the schema.org type.

For this reason, Bioschemas²³ has been developed. Bioschemas specifies "profiles" over schema.org types. The profile constrains a schema.org type to be sensible for Bioinformatics purposes. A Bioschemas profile specifies which properties are mandatory (minimal), recommended and optional. It also states the cardinality of a property, i.e. how many values are expected, and sometimes constrains the values that can be specified for that property. Bioschemas's "Organization"²⁴ shows how the generic Organization can be constrained.

Bioschemas also supports the proposal of new types to be added to the schema.org hierarchy.

Impact on IBISBA

IBISBA WP7 as part of the WorkflowHub Club have guided the submission of new types for ComputationalWorkflow²⁵ and FormalParameter²⁶ (representing a parameter of the workflow).

IBISBAHub, WorkflowHub and FAIRDOMHub all support schema.org annotation. In the wider domain it is supported by bio.tools (see below) and provides a basis for describing the content of Research Objects.

The use of common annotation allows significantly more federation of IBISBAHub with other tools and systems.

3.5 Bio.tools and the EDAM ontology

bio.tools²⁷ is a project to develop a comprehensive registry of software and databases. This includes a wide range of tools from simple command-line tools and online services, through to databases and executable workflows. bio.tools allows researchers in biological and biomedical science to find, understand, utilise and cite the resources that they use.

bio.tools holds information about a very large number of services, over 17 000 in October 2020. The tools are annotated with terms from the EDAM ontology, In addition the tool descriptions are versioned.

²¹ <https://datasetsearch.research.google.com/>

²² <https://schema.org/Organization>

²³ <https://bioschemas.org/>

²⁴ <https://bioschemas.org/profiles/Organization/>

²⁵ https://bioschemas.org/types/ComputationalWorkflow/0.1-DRAFT-2020_07_21

²⁶ https://bioschemas.org/types/FormalParameter/0.1-DRAFT-2020_07_21

²⁷ <https://bio.tools/>

"EDAM is an ontology of well established, familiar concepts that are prevalent within bioinformatics, including types of data and data identifiers, data formats, operations and topics. EDAM is a simple ontology - essentially a set of terms with synonyms and definitions - organised into an intuitive hierarchy for convenient use by curators, software developers and end-users. EDAM is suitable for large-scale semantic annotations and categorisation of diverse bioinformatics resources. EDAM is also suitable for diverse application including for example within workbenches and workflow-management systems, software distributions, and resource registries."

The tools registered in bio.tools are exposed in a user interface and in an API that allows the listing, creation, reading, updating and deletion of the tool. The API uses a bio.tools specific JSON description of the tool. Importantly, bio.tools has recently extended the API to allow the exposure of the tool in JSON-LD that contains schema.org annotations as **SoftwareApplication**²⁸

bio.tools is funded by ELIXIR through the ELIXIR-EXCELERATE grant, which is funded by the European Union.

Impact on IBISBA

IBISBAHub was designed to register the tools (called nodes) used by IBISBA. As such, it strongly overlaps. In a similar manner to that for workflows, IBISBA WP7 has decided that **bio.tools is the preferred registry of IBISBA tools**. IBISBAHub will present its users with "proxies" to tools registered in bio.tools.

4 Handbook

In WP7 we have been working on putting together a handbook²⁷, which will serve as a user guide for the current and future members of the IBISBA community. The aim of the handbook is to be a complete guide providing adequate information and instructions required for successfully running an IBISBA project in line with the principles and processes set by the IBISBA consortium. The handbook is a work in progress and will cover the general information about IBISBA, outlining its purpose and scope, together with IBISBA Subsidized Access (previously TNAs).

The IBISBAHub is obviously an important section of the handbook and it provides a detailed guide to use the hub. The handbook:

- Guides project and facility operators to manage the organisation, exchange, and reporting of their results in the IBISBAHub at each stage of the experiment with the help of examples
- Guides projects and facility operators on how to deposit, save, and selectively share SOP's, Datafiles, Assays
- Guides projects and facility operators on how to register Datafiles, Assays stored at their own

²⁸ <https://schema.org/SoftwareApplication>

²⁸ <https://ibisba.github.io/handbook/>

facilities, and how to control access for other project members.

- Helps projects with advice on IBISBA's chosen standards for data

5 User engagement

We have held multiple events to engage the IBISBA community and familiarise them with the usage and benefits of IBISBAHub. IBISBAHub was introduced to the community via one-on-one sessions with the facility managers as well as at IBISBA events. The IBISBAHub was presented at IBISBA Virtual Consortium Meeting held on the 9th of July, 2020. In the same event we also introduced the IBISBA handbook and solicited active participation of the community for contribution towards the content of the handbook. This was followed by the one-to-one sessions with the facilities where we addressed the various issues pertaining to the usage of the IBISBAHub and how it could facilitate the data management process and sharing for the TNA's which these facilities were executing.

In addition to these sessions, a virtual hands-on training workshop was held on 9th September 2020, as part of the Internal Workshop on IBISBAHub and Harmonization.

All IBISBA facility operators and other interested community members were trained to use the IBISBAHub. This was done by setting up a training instance of the IBISBAHub and giving the participants the opportunity to use and explore the features of the IBISBAHub in the presence of the IBISBAHub developers and community workers.

We have also formed a IBISBAHub club and invited all the IBISBA facilities to become a part of this club; the club will allow us to disseminate and discuss the usage, features and improvements that can benefit the users. We plan to hold regular meetings of the IBISBAHub club to gain feedback and suggestions from the users; this will be invaluable for the improvement of the IBISBAHub.

6 Collaboration with wider community

The developers of IBISBAHub collaborate closely with other developers; this includes taking part in a number of committees, most of which meet online (virtually).

6.1 SEEK Committees

WP7 is represented on two FAIRDOM SEEK Committees – the SEEK Technical Committee that meets every week and the Community Workers meeting that meets once a month. In addition, both committees have mailing lists and slack channels for more frequent conversation.

The SEEK Technical Committee is made up of the technical developers of SEEK, and aligns the work being done by different teams. It also is responsible for the scheduling, content and production of SEEK releases. The SEEK Technical Committee includes representatives from the University of Manchester, VIB-UGent Center for Plant Systems Biology and from the Heidelberg Institute for Theoretical Studies.

The IBISBA representatives have been involved in much of the SEEK developments, especially of the SEEK API.

The SEEK Community Workers meeting brings together representatives of the users of SEEK. They discuss issues that they share, and forward them to the SEEK Technical Committee. For example, IBISBA have discussed the representation and sharing of sample information.

6.2 WorkflowHub Club

The WorkflowHub Club²⁹ provides technical direction for the WorkflowHub. The WorkflowHub Club has over 50 members and is chaired by Frederik Coppens from VIB-UGent Center for Plant Systems Biology. It has representatives of numerous Workflow systems and infrastructures, including Galaxy, Nextflow and Snakemake.

The WorkflowHub Club meets weekly (changing to every two weeks) and also provides a forum for the discussion of integration with Workflow systems, of events and of Workflow related initiatives and collaborations. One initiative to note is the work with Bioschemas (see below).

6.3 Bioschemas Community

IBISBA and other members of the WorkflowHub Club are part of the Bioschemas Community. Representatives of IBISBA WP7 have helped to develop the ComputationalWorkflow type and profile. They are in close collaboration with the creators of the ComputationalTool profile and have discussed harmonization and interfacing of tools and workflows. WP7 have also maintained a “watching brief” on the proposals for metadata for LabProtocols.

The Bioschemas Community call takes place monthly. Its main topics are the development and adoption of Bioschemas types/profiles, implementation studies and forthcoming meetings, including hackathons.

6.4 Biohackathons

Representatives of IBISBA WP7 take part in Bioinformatics related hackathons³⁰. Recent hackathons include

- the COVID Virtual Biohackathon³¹ (April 5th – 11th 2020)
- Biohackathon Europe³²
 - November 12th - 16th 2018 in Paris
 - November 18th – 22nd 2019 in Paris
 - November 9th – 13th Virtual

The Biohackathons are a great opportunity for concentrated development and interaction with developers on related (closely or otherwise) projects. For example, in the Biohackathon Europe 2020, virtual

²⁹ <https://about.workflowhub.eu/acknowledgements/>

³⁰ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hackathon>

³¹ <http://www.datascience.manchester.ac.uk/events-1/events/covid-19-virtual-bio-hackathon/>

³² <https://www.biohackathon-europe.org/>

discussions have taken place with the ISATools community, the ShEx Wikidata projects and on GA4GH workflow execution.

6.5 Research Object Communities

The main Research Object Crate community calls take place every month. IBISBA WP7 has two representatives on the calls. The topics include the RO-Crate specifications, implementations and upcoming events.

Specific calls will take place every two weeks centred on the needs for Workflow execution representation in RO-Crate.

IBISBA WP7 representatives have contributed to and reviewed both the RO-Crate 1.1 specification and its Workflow profile.

7 Future work

This section presents some of the highlights of the planned work on IBISBAHub.

7.1 Workflow execution

A proposal for **running workflows** in future is presented in [MS36](#).

7.2 Investigation planning and enactment

IBISBAHub is able to represent both enacted investigations and also investigations that are planned to be carried out. The creation of planned investigations is enabled by the populator tool within IBISBAHub and its interaction with VTT's DBTL-U Task Curation (TasCu)³³ system. The information that is relevant to a planned investigation differs from that for recording of an enacted investigation. For example, a planned investigation will expect to take some input of a given type, whereas an enacted investigation will specify the actual input that was consumed, also parts of a planned investigation may fail or be abandoned, whereas such failures are normally not recorded.

The differences between a planned investigation and an enactment will be implemented in IBISBAHub, while ensuring consistency with existing code.

7.3 Protocols

WP6's work to curate and ensure standardization of the protocols will be supported. The proposals for "meta-protocols" (grouping of the atomic protocols) will also be handled. Discussion with representatives of WP6 is taking place on both these topics.

³³ <https://tascu.vtt.fi/tascu>

The relationship between protocols and assay types is being investigated in conjunction with representatives from the Minimum Information About a Plant Phenotyping Experiment (MIAPPE)³⁴ project, and also from ISATools³⁵. The results of this work will impact IBISBA in the longer term.

7.4 BPM execution

Business process modelling will enable the tracking and enactment of investigations within IBISBA. Possible BPM engines, such as Activiti³⁶ (the open source variant of Alfresco) and Flowable³⁷ have been evaluated.

There are two main topics that remain to be considered in detail:

- The mapping from a planned investigation (or a meta-protocol) to a BPM
- The tracking of progress through a BPM execution.

The latter may, of course, be done manually, and this may be adopted as a solution for the demonstrator (D7.4). Longer term, it would be better if the BPM system could automatically monitor when data is produced / consumed by an infrastructure. This would, of course, entail extensive collaboration with the infrastructures.

8 Partners involved in the work

UNIMAN: Alan Williams, Carole Goble, Munazah Andrabi

WUR: Jasper Koehorst

VTT: Gopal Peddinti, Peter Blomberg

INRA: Melchior Du-Lac

KNIME: Stefan Helfrich

³⁴ <https://www.miappe.org/>

³⁵ <https://isa-tools.org/>

³⁶ <https://www.activiti.org/>

³⁷ <https://flowable.com/>